

PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATION OF TRAINING ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS OF HIGHER EDUCATION BASED ON INNOVATIVE APPROACHES

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ABSTRACT: The introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies at all educational levels that fully comply with international standards is one of the main tasks facing the country's education system. This article describes some theoretical and methodological aspects of the organization of innovative work of English teachers, analyzes the essence of innovation and innovation, describes the areas for preparing future English teachers for innovation and their psychological and pedagogical conditions. It also discusses innovative methods used in the US education system for teaching foreign languages.

Keywords: foreign language, future English teachers, innovation, innovation, sugestopedia, jigsaw reading, Socratic seminar, philosophical chair

It is known that in recent years special attention has been paid in our country to the issue of teaching foreign languages to young people and training mature specialists who can meet the requirements of the times for various spheres of society. Because a perfect knowledge of a foreign language, along with being aware of events in foreign countries, achievements in the field of science and technology, innovative educational methods, and the great creativity and creative work carried out in our country, and the positive results achieved gives an opportunity to be introduced to the world public. On January 24, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan ShavkatMirziyoyev's address to the OliyMajlis stated: we can achieve with innovation. For this, first of all, it is necessary to educate the new generation of personnel who will be proactive reformers, who think strategically, and who will be educated and qualified".

In order for talented students studying at HEIs specialized in language teaching to master foreign languages perfectly, it is required to use advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, and communication and information tools during the training sessions. In our republic, new methods and requirements for foreign language teaching and evaluation of knowledge and skills of future foreign language teachers are being developed in accordance with the European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). Accordingly, the most important task facing the higher education system today is the development of innovative pedagogical activities of future English language

teachers, the application of advanced foreign experiences to the educational process, and the use of information and communication technologies. special attention is being paid to raising the quality of education and training competitive mature specialists in accordance with the requirements. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev dated April 20, 2017 No. 2909 "On measures for further development of the higher education system", dated August 29, 2017 No. PQ-3245 "Information on measures to further improve the project management system in the field of communication technologies", PQ-3365 dated November 1, 2017 "On measures to further strengthen the infrastructure of scientific research institutions and develop innovative activities", The decision and decree No. PF-5264 of November 29, 2017 "On the establishment of the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" serves as a programmatic action in the effective organization and management of educational processes in our country.

In the literature, innovation problems have long been studied in the framework of economic research. But over time, innovative changes began to appear in all spheres of social life. Before thinking about innovative activities of higher education English language teachers or innovative education, let's take a closer look at the concept of "innovation". means "innovation".

According to the "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan", innovation has the following content and concepts: "Innovation (innovations" - introduced innovation, invention) - 1) funds spent on the economy to ensure the replacement of technology and technology generations ; 2) innovations in the fields of engineering, technology, management and labor organization based on scientific and technical achievements and best practices, as well as their application in various fields and spheres of activity". While I. Schumpeter and N. Kondratev are considered the first and greatest theorists of the concept of "Innovation", K. Angelovsky, VASlastenin and VISlobadchikov tried to prove in their scientific research that innovative activity is a special form of pedagogical activity, and the scientists who achieved certain results in this regard, are recognized.

The aim is to obtain the highest possible result from the spent money and effort in the application of innovations in the educational system or educational activities. Innovation differs from any innovation in that it needs to have a changeable mechanism that allows for management and control.

T.M. Davidenko emphasized that the three necessary conditions for mastering any pedagogical innovation should be "understanding, reflection and

personal readiness". Today, it is important for future English language teachers to have innovative skills and competencies. Deciding on an innovative approach is also a complex process that takes place in several stages. That is:

Stage 1: ready-made methodical recommendations (existing innovations) are used.

Stage 2: introduces new ideas, methods into the existing system.

Step 3: systematizes the content, form and methods of implementing a new idea.

Stage 4: the pedagogue creates his own concept or methodology of teaching and training.

It became clear from the analysis that the English language teaching process cannot be organized without an innovative factor. For this reason, it is important to study effective methods abroad and organize the teacher's innovative-pedagogical activities based on them. Therefore, at the stage of implementation of new qualitative changes in foreign language teaching in our country, purposeful preparation of students as competitive specialists for the growth of the country's economy is the main requirement of today. Below we will introduce innovative methods of teaching foreign languages that are widely used in the US education system.

At the same time, in the USA, as in a number of other skills, the innovative methodology known as "suggestopedia" has developed widely. This method, related to the intensification of education and hypnosis, has been variously evaluated, criticized, and applauded. However, its results are surprising. Educators who teach on the basis of Suggestopedia undergo special training. In this way, maximum favorable conditions are created for learners to quickly learn a new language. Each student is convinced that he has extraordinary linguistic abilities, the lesson is conducted with the help of movement and games, as well as musical effects to facilitate the reception of the material, multimedia tools are constantly used, etc. When using this method, the speed of language learning increases 40-50 times, because the number of words and sentences memorized per day is much higher than the numbers in the usual method (the recorded record is about a thousand words and phrases in one day).

"Jigsaw reading" is a method used to develop students' reading, speaking and reasoning skills. This method is especially effective when working with short stories, texts and articles. It is done as follows. Students are divided into two groups.

The first group is given the first part of the story, the second group is given

the second part of the story. Students will have to read and memorize the part of the story given to them. Then each student is selected pairs from the other group. Each pair tells each other the story they read. At the end of the work, a complete story will appear in each pair. Students can make some notes to help them remember the story. At the end of the game, you can also use question and answer to reinforce the topic. This type of work on the text can be organized in a different way. Students of the first group are given the text with words or sentences deleted from it. The members of the second group are given completely different words and sentences without deletion. The members of both groups should complete their text by asking questions.

"Socratic seminar" this method is based on the teaching method of the famous philosopher Socrates by asking countless questions. The teacher gives the students a text covering the required topic and time to prepare. By asking a series of questions, the teacher will find out how well the students have understood the topic.

The "Philosophical chair" method is similar to a debate. Students will be given the main topic and questions. They can agree, disagree or remain neutral. This method is based on students having a lively discussion with each other and learning new things from each other. Each student takes turns sitting on a chair in the center and expressing their thoughts. Then the discussion begins.

"CALL" (Computer Assisted Language Learning) is a language learning aid direction called computer resources, in which multimedia programs are developed for any stage. Online learning systems "BYKI" and "Edmodo" [6] are educational systems programmed according to the model of social networks, which are currently popular. The teacher communicates with his students remotely. Manages the language learning process, designs, conducts various tests. Learners can also communicate and perform their tasks. They can also use the teacher's personal library.

"Global Stimulation" program - a set of case studies in different languages, etc. The above are educational resources and innovative methods used in language education worldwide. It is appropriate to use these language methods in the process of training future English language teachers in HEIs of our Republic.

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